

Inverse and Dualverse Skyscraper Concept

A **skyscraper** is a tall continuously habitable building having multiple floors.

An **inverse skyscraper** is a tall habitable building, just like a regular skyscraper, that is built underneath the ground. In simple words, it is built downwards instead of upwards.

A **dualverse skyscraper** is a combination of both a skyscraper and inverse skyscraper. It's built both upwards and downwards.

Skyscraper

Inverse Skyscraper

Dualverse skyscraper

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